

Data curator: who is she/he?

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Abstract

The Workshop has introduced the project recently funded by the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), under the auspices of its Library Theory and Research Section. The main aim of the project is to identify the characteristics of the tasks and the responsibilities of data curators, in both the international and interdisciplinary contexts. This IFLA project is surveying a representative set of data curators and their institutions, in order to develop a “data curator ontology” that should help to better define the profession and develop appropriate educational curricula. . The starting point for the discussion in this workshop is based on what we learned in developing a Glossary and the identification of other problematic areas discovered in the process of exploring and ontology for data curation. The workshop also presented the preliminary findings from the content analysis of job announcements selected from a variety of library and information science job posting sites.

Key words: Data curator; Open Science; Cyber-infrastructure; Open data; Research Data Management

1. Introduction

The role of data curator has become an important position, stimulated by the emerging need of curating data produced by scholars and government and research institutions. Is this the role of data scientists? Or cultural heritage professionals? Or computer scientists? or is it a completely new role?

Recent studies are providing valuable input towards constructing this understanding. Among these, there is a project recently funded by the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), under the auspices of its Library Theory and Research Section. The main aim of the project is to identify the characteristics of the tasks and the responsibilities of data curators, in both the international and interdisciplinary contexts. This IFLA project surveys a representative set of data curators and their institutions, in order to develop a “data curator ontology” that should help to define the profession and provide assistance in developing appropriate educational curricula. In this workshop we are sharing the preliminary results of our survey and exploring areas in need of further investigation as we proceed in our research.

The main goal of the Workshop has been to achieve understanding of the main trends in Europe in the interdisciplinary and international research in managing data collections and related areas. The Workshop has stimulated the discussion on a shared vocabulary, to understand the different aspects of the data curation in Europe, where most of participants came from. Countries of participants were: France, Finland, Germany, Italy, Netherland, Switzerland and U.S.

The expected participants in this Workshop were information professionals (data curators, librarians, data managers, etc.) involved in the management and preservation of research data, scholars interested in understanding the new requirements for publishing research results, representatives of memory institutions (potential employers of information professionals), teachers and educators from institutions providing education and training to future information professionals. Workshop participants were instead mostly students (43%) and teachers (37%), with a minority of professionals of which two of them were working as data curator and have been later interviewed.

2.Data curator

The Workshop organizers have briefly reported on the ongoing results of the IFLA Project “Data curator: who is she/he?”. Much of the research done so far has been concentrated in the U.S., where the role has been started for years, with responsibilities that over time have become clearer and more specific. In Europe, the Nordic countries were the first to launch research initiatives and professional good practices on the role of data curator.

2.1 Data curator: U.S. research and practice

Terry Weech and Krystyna Matusiak presented the U.S. research and practice.

Terry Weech posed the following questions for discussion

- What education do professionals in Data Curation share with other information professionals?
- What are the related information professions to Data Curation?
- How do the duties and skills of professionals such as Data Scientists, eScientists, Information Scientists, and Librarians compare to the skills of a Data Curator?

The University of Illinois’ Graduate School of Library and Information Science defines data

curation¹ as:

“the active and ongoing management of data through its life cycle of interest and usefulness to scholarship, science, and education. Data curation activities enable data discovery and retrieval, maintain its quality, add value, and provide for reuse over time, and this new field includes authentication, archiving, management, preservation, retrieval, and representation.”

Examples of different terms use in the U.S. in educational programs on Data Curation:

Data Scientist (Wisconsin, U.S.²)

“University of Wisconsin online Master of Science in Data Science will teach you how to clean, organize, analyze, and interpret unstructured data, deriving knowledge and communicating your discoveries clearly using sophisticated visualization techniques and other means”.

eScience and Data Science (Syracuse University, U.S.³)

“What is eScience? eScience is computationally intensive science that is carried out in highly distributed network environments. (via Wikipedia)”

Data Curation Specialization at the University of Illinois, U.S.⁴:

“The specialization prepares students to plan and manage data curation systems, create and maintain data collections, and evaluate and apply data and metadata standards for varied U.S.es across the sciences, humanities, and social sciences”.

The Data Curation Specialization may be earned either as part of an ALA-accredited Master of Science (MS) degree or, for students who have already completed their master’s degree, as part of a Certificate of Advanced Study (CAS)⁵. Students in the data curation specialization work with their advisors to select electives for an individualized program that will prepare them for either a general or specialized career path.

¹ <http://www.clir.org/initiatives-partnerships/data-curation>

² http://info.wisconsin.edu/ds/?lead_source=PaidSearchGoogle&kw=data%20scientist&_bt=93573151754&_bm=p&gclid=CjwKEAiAzuK0BRCW4tiLpJT-8TISJADV8cw9Ff8JKWgfjuK8sg58fSzFMOzCm8xiNb2myoiMQqS5xoC6fPw_wcB

³ <http://infospace.ischool.syr.edu/2010/10/18/title-be-damned-escience-at-the-ischool/>

⁴ https://www.lis.illinois.edu/academics/degrees/specializations/data_curation

⁵ In a 40 hour Master’s in LIS - Required for the Specialization (3 courses below plus two from Recommended Electives) Total of 20 hours.

LIS531 Foundations of Data Curation

LIS562 Metadata in Theory and Practice*

LIS586 Digital Preservation

Recommended Electives

Students must take two (2) courses from this list; taking four (4) is advised.

LIS452 Foundations of Information Processing in LIS

LIS453 Systems Analysis and Management*

LIS490DB Introduction to Databases

LIS560 Digital Libraries

LIS561 Information Modeling

LIS590OD Ontology Development

LIS590RO Representing and Organizing Information Resources

From 2013 through 2015, 62 students in the Illinois LIS Master's Degree program earned a specialization in Data Curation.

A survey distributed in 2014⁶ (Palmer et al. 2014) found that of the 2008-2012 graduates with a Data Curation specialization, 48% who responded were in what they considered to be data curation positions. Most of those not in Data Curation positions felt that the skills learned in data curation were helpful in their current jobs. Most were working in library positions. In 2011 survey⁷ of graduates, only 2 out of the 12 that hoped for a Data Curation position found one.

Krystyna Matusiak presented the empirical part of the IFLA Data Curation project focused on examining job announcements in order to identify competencies and skills required of data curators. In the first phase of the project, the research team conducted content analysis of job announcements for data curators in the U.S. The goal of analyzing job postings was to examine the titles used for data curation positions and to understand what are the roles and qualifications of data curators. This approach presents the employer perspective but it allows to see what terminology is being used and what are the expectations of people hired for these positions.

For the purpose of this project, a variety of library and information science job posting sites were searched to identify position announcements with data curation responsibilities, including:

- American Library Association (ALA) Job list⁸
- Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR)⁹
- Code4lib¹⁰
- Indeed: one search all jobs¹¹
- Selected data curation centers.

The initial review process yielded 60 current and past position announcements. Data curation was identified as a primary responsibility in 42 reviewed positions, while data curation was listed as preferred or secondary function in 18 positions focused on digital preservation, digital collections, digital library development, science librarianship, or repository services and software development. Data curation appears as an additional responsibility in the position announcements for Digital Repositories Archivists, Digital Collection Librarians, Data Repository Outreach Specialists, Repository Developers, Digital Preservation Librarians, and Science Librarians.

The sample of 42 positions with data curation as a primary responsibility was analyzed further in regard to geographic location, educational qualifications, responsibilities, and required and preferred knowledge and skills. The preliminary analysis of the sample indicates a wide range of

⁶ Palmer, C. L., Thompson, C. A., Baker, K. S., & Senseney, M. (2014). Meeting Data Workforce Needs: Indicators Based on Recent Data Curation Placements. In *iConference 2014 Proceedings* (p. 522–537). doi:10.9776/14133

⁷ From 2011 GSLIS alum survey “UI-GSLIS Placement” An unpublished internally distributed report.

⁸ <http://joblist.ala.org/>

⁹ <http://www.clir.org/fellowships/postdoc/info/dc-science>

¹⁰ <http://jobs.code4lib.org/jobs/data-curation/>

¹¹ <http://www.indeed.com/>

position titles. Certain titles appeared multiple times, including: Data Curation Librarian, Digital Curation, Data Curator, Data Management Librarian, Data Services Librarian, Repository Librarian, and Scholarly Communications Librarian.

There is also a broad range of required educational qualifications in the analyzed sample from Bachelor's degrees to PhDs. However, it is worth noting that 18 positions in the sample (N=42) require Master of Library or Information Science degree from the program accredited by the American Library Association (ALA). In several position announcements with minimum qualifications of Bachelor's or Master's degree in a relevant field, ALA-accredited Master of Library or Information Science degree was listed as desired. The PhD requirement appears primarily in the postdoctoral fellowships in data curation sponsored by the Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR). Subject expertise in a specific field is often listed as required and desired.

Responsibilities of data curation librarians and specialists focus on data curation and data management but also involve a wide range of other functions such as policy development, copyright advice, open access advocacy, data analysis using quantitative and qualitative software, information visualization, and repository services. Many positions require competency in statistical data software, knowledge of metadata standards, and familiarity with open access repository software, such as DSpace or Fedora. The responsibilities of data curation librarians in the academic library setting often involve interdisciplinary work and building bridges between a library and campus departments or specialized centers.

In the second phase of the project, the research team plans to expand the scope of job analysis by including international postings from sites such as the Job Repository of the Science Information Services and Technology (IASSIST). Moreover, data collection activities will include interviews with data curators in several countries. Interviews will provide an opportunity to gain insight into the practice of data curation and look at the roles and responsibilities from the perspective of information professionals working in the field.

2.2 Data curator: Nordic countries research and practice

Heidi Kristin Olsen has introduced the situation in the Nordic countries where there are quite a lot of activities about research data management at the moment. The situation is growing due to the impact of the European recommendations and the following implementation of national strategies. Many of these new national strategies focus on data development plan. However there are still few positions as Data Curator in the job descriptions and none of these is mentioning a specific LIS education and training.

The words mostly used in Nordic countries focus on Data handling (Tab. 1):

Norwegian	Danish	Swedish	Translation
Datahåndtering / Håndtering av forskningsdata	Datahåndtering	Datahantering	Data handling

Forskningsdata håndtering	Forskningsdata håndtering	Hantering av Forskningsmaterial / forskningsdata	Research data handling
Datakurator	Datakurator	Datakurator	Data curator
Dataforvaltning	Dataforvaltning	Dataförvaltning	Data management
Databevaring	Databevaring	Databevarande	Data conservation

Tab. 1 Words used in Nordic countries

2.3 Data curator: Workshop participants discussion

In Europe the role of data curator seems still confused. The Open Science Programme of the European Commission (2010)¹², however, is having an impact on the perception of the need for this role for curating the research data, so the situation is changing.

Small group discussion has been stimulated to encourage participants to share their opinions and perceptions of the data curator role.

The group discussion has been focused on two questions:

- What is the data curator definition that participants believe is the most suitable?
- Librarians have the skills to take the responsibility of the role of data curator?

Replying to the first question, all the definitions given during the Workshop focus on two areas: data management and data access.

Area	Tasks and responsibilities
Data management	To handle data, to preserve it and make it accessible To add metadata, unlocking data, data enrichment To assure compatibility of data; quality checking of data; To maintain or identifying repositories To do preservation of data
Data access	Data analyst, a former documentation person or librarian, to support and visualise

¹² European Union (2010) Riding the Wave: How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data. Final report of the High level Expert Group on Scientific Data
<http://cordis.europa.eu/fp7/ict/e-infrastructure/docs/hlg-sdi-report.pdf>

	<p>the analysis of data</p> <p>Specialised librarian, able to seek information for researchers</p> <p>To ensure data in its lifecycle and in any knowledge sector, research, etc.</p> <p>To collect data from different studies and makes it readable and available for other scientists (and public!)</p>
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Replying to the second question, the answers of majority of participants (coming from library sector) were so generic:

I do not really know, I am here to learn about this profile. In my mind it seems to be a digital librarian who makes with technical or scientific data

A data curator works in a library and collect data (retrieval) and manages it using Information System (manage) to allow people to re-use that data for a certain amount of time

While the answers obtained by the two participants who were data manager showed a different approach by librarians:

A data curator helps with building bridges between specialized companies

There are two levels of qualification: the first is Computer scientists (with a Master); the second is Curating the data (with a Bachelor). Data science training is needed for librarians (for example @DST4L in 2016 event¹³).

The second question about librarians' capability to be a data curator showed contrasting views. Some see the data curator profile a different profile from the librarian. Although they may agree to assign this role to librarians, however, they warn that they must receive appropriate training and have the knowledge management background

Not always, some are, skills set is similar but not identical

A traditional librarian will not be a data curator as such. A knowledge manager might be one.

The majority however believes that the librarian has the skills to take on this responsibility:

Yes, both have the same purpose: retrieving and present relevant data or in any case making it accessible

LIS professionals opening up data (resources) with the help of metadata, taxonomies, ontologies. They do not analyse data they make them accesible for other researchers

Some of them are if they are PUSH people, it is a matter of motivation, personal qualities, technical abilities

This difference in approach has resulted in different opinions with respect to the education and training and necessary updating. Some believe that the library already has all the necessary skills. But others point out that there is a training gap for two competencies area, identified as technology skills as well as specific domain expertise.

LIS professionals are more than data curators but it should be part of LIS education

¹³ Data Scientist Training for Librarians (#DST4L) is an experimental course at the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, John G. Wolbach Library, intended to upgrade the skills of librarians so that they can respond to the changing needs of patrons, especially when it comes to research data, and hopefully become invaluable contributors to the data scientist community. In the course, they have covered data science topics, worked hands-on with software such as OpenRefine, programmed in languages such as Python and R, and had notable data scientist guest speakers join the class to either present or provide training.

They could if they learn data curators competencies in software, programming languages or information research

Conclusions

The starting point for the discussion in this workshop is based on what we learned in developing a Glossary and the identification of other problematic areas discovered in the process of exploring an ontology for data curation. The workshop also presented the preliminary findings from the content analysis of job announcements selected from a variety of library and information science job posting sites.

The Workshop evidenced the need of sharing concepts and theories about an evolving specialised role, which is interdisciplinary and international. The organizers will continue the dialog begun at BOBCATSSS through the IFLA Project Website.

References

European Union (2010) Riding the Wave: How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data. Final report of the High level Expert Group on Scientific Data
<http://cordis.europa.eu/fp7/ict/e-infrastructure/docs/hlg-sdi-report.pdf>